

An Expert-Driven Validation of Data Quality Domains in Medical Big Data

This questionnaire is designed to validate the identified **Data Quality Domains (DQDs)** in **Medical Big Data (MBD)** as part of a research study. You are requested to evaluate each data quality domain based on its **Relevance, Completeness, Clarity, Applicability & Usability, and Sufficiency** using your domain expertise. All responses will be kept confidential and used solely for academic research purposes.

* Required

Expert Profile

Expert Demographics and Professional Background

1. Name of the expert/professional *

2. Designation *

3. Address of an organization *

4. Years of experience *

5. Area of expertise *

6. Email address *

Evaluation and Validation of the **Technical Data Quality Domain** in Medical Big Data

Technical—Structural and syntactic correctness. **Definition:** Low-level properties that make sure data is machine-readable and adheres to data schemas and fundamental validation rules and the **attributes, such as completeness, accuracy, consistency, uniqueness, timeliness, validity, integrity, and reliability.** **Example:** Lab results stored with required fields (test code, value, units) and validated ranges; duplicates are removed, so that each patient’s ID is unique. **How to measure:** % complete fields, duplicate rate, and schema validation pass rates. **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

7. How relevant is the Technical Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

8. To what extent does the Technical Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

9. How clear and well-defined is the Technical Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

10. How applicable and easy to use is the Technical Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11. To what extent is the Technical Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Contextual Data Quality Domain** in Medical Big Data

Contextual—Fitness for a specific task. **Definition:** Data are appropriate and useful for the intended clinical/analytical purpose and the **attributes, such as relevance, granularity, interpretability, contextual accessibility, contextual validity, fitness for use, contextual adequacy and representativeness** . **Example:** Using minute-level vital signs for ICU trend detection (good contextual fit) versus daily aggregates (poor fit for real-time alerts). **How to measure:** Coverage of task-required variables and clinician relevance ratings . **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

12. How relevant is the Contextual Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

13. To what extent does the Contextual Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

14. How clear and well-defined is the Contextual Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

15. How applicable and easy to use is the Contextual Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

16. To what extent is the Contextual Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Semantic Data Quality Domain** in Medical Big Data

Semantic—Correct meaning and terminology. **Definition:** Meaning-level correctness: consistent use of controlled vocabularies/ontologies such as Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine (SNOMED), Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC), correct concept mapping and the absence of ambiguous or conflicting terms and **attributes, such as semantic consistency, semantic accuracy, ontology alignment, semantic richness, concept harmonization, terminology uniformity, semantic completeness, semantic clarity** . **Example:** Mapping "MI" and "Myocardial infarction" can be mapped to the same SNOMED code, ensuring that laboratory tests use standard LOINC codes . **How to measure:** % of records mapped to standard codes and the number of ambiguous terms detected. **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

17. How relevant is the Semantic Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

18. To what extent does the Semantic Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

19. How clear and well-defined is the Semantic Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

20. How applicable and easy to use is the Semantic Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

21. To what extent is the Semantic Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Governance & Security Data Quality Domain** in MBD

Governance & Security—Rules, roles, legal, and ethical protections. **Definition:** Policies, stewardship, access controls, consent management, auditability and legal/regulatory compliance that protect data and define responsibilities and **attributes such as consent validity, access control, privacy & confidentiality, regulatory compliance, role-based governance, data ownership & stewardship, auditability/audit trail, transparency.** **Example:** Role-based access, which prevents junior staff from viewing identifiable genetic data, and audit log recording, which exports a dataset. **How to measure:** % records with valid consent, number of policy violations, and audit-trail completeness. **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

22. How relevant is the Governance & Security Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

23. To what extent does the Governance & Security Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

24. How clear and well-defined is the Governance & Security Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

25. How applicable and easy to use is the Governance & Security Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

26. To what extent is the Governance & Security Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Analytical/Statistical Data Quality Domain** in MBD

Analytical/Statistical—Fit for Modeling and inference. **Definition:** Statistical properties important for analysis and ML. And attributes, such as **Missingness patterns, bias, outliers, variance, representativeness, inferential validity, robustness, and signal-to-noise ratio.** **Example:** A training cohort that over-represents one age group (introducing bias) or widespread missingness in ethnic fields harms fairness analysis. **How to measure:** Missingness%, bias metrics, drift detection scores, and Signal-to-noise Ratio. **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

27. How relevant is the Analytical/Statistical Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

28. To what extent does the Analytical/Statistical Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

29. How clear and well-defined is the Analytical/Statistical Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

30. How applicable and easy to use is the Analytical/Statistical Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

31. To what extent is the Analytical/Statistical Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Temporal Data Quality Domain** in MBD

Temporal—Time Correctness and Coherence. **Definition:** Time-related qualities such as timeliness, latency, synchronization, frequency, recency and temporal coherence (no impossible timestamps) and **attributes, such as temporal currency, latency/punctuality, temporal plausibility, temporal stability, temporal continuity, state transition validity, temporal granularity, and versioning & lineage accuracy.** **Example:** Continuous monitor readings arriving with >5-minute delay (latency), or lab orders timestamped after result times (chronology error) . **How to measure:** median latency, % out-of-order timestamps, and freshness age . **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

32. How relevant is the Temporal Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

33. To what extent does the Temporal Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

34. How clear and well-defined is the Temporal Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

35. How applicable and easy to use is the Temporal Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

36. To what extent is the Temporal Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Operational/Workflow Data Quality Domain** in MBD

Operational/Workflow—How do data fit into human and system processes? **Definition:** Alignment with clinical/workflow processes: whether data collection/entry patterns and notifications support (not hinder) clinical work—addresses template bias, alerts fatigue, and integration with Electronic Medical Record (EMR) flows and **attributes, such as workflow conformance, system usability, alert fatigue, logging burden, data capture latency, user access control, audit trail completeness, and role-specific entry accuracy.** **Example:** Pre-filled default No Known Allergies (NKA) causing missed allergy entries, and too many non-actionable alerts causing clinicians to ignore warnings . **How to measure:** template-override rate, clinician time-to-find information, and alert dismissal rate be measured . **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

37. How relevant is the Operational/Workflow Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

38. To what extent does the Operational/Workflow Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

39. How clear and well-defined is the Operational/Workflow Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

40. How applicable and easy to use is the Operational/Workflow Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

41. To what extent is the Operational/Workflow Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Provenance/Source Data Quality Domain** in MBD

Provenance/Source—Where data came from and how they moved. **Definition:** Traceability and lineage: identifying the original device/user/system, transformations applied, and chain-of-custody for each datum and **attributes, such as source identification, provenance tracking, data generation context, source system heterogeneity, acquisition device details, original documentation linkage, recording responsibility, and multi-source attribution** . **Example:** A lab value record that stores the instrument serial number, software version, processing steps and who approved the results . **How to measure:** % records with full lineage metadata and provenance integrity checks. **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

42. How relevant is the Provenance/Source Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

43. To what extent does the Provenance/Source Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

44. How clear and well-defined is the Provenance/Source Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

45. How applicable and easy to use is the Provenance/Source Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

46. To what extent is the Provenance/Source Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Metadata & Documentation Data Quality Domain** in MBD

Metadata & Documentation—Human-readable descriptions that explain data. **Definition:** Data dictionaries, schemas, field definitions, units, and versioning and processing notes that allow people and tools to correctly understand and reuse data and **attributes, such as metadata completeness, data dictionary availability, provenance documentation, versioning, annotation quality, codebook availability, semantic interoperability documentation, contextual metadata.** **Example:** A dataset README and field glossary listing units for “glucose” (mg/dL) and update the history for each table. **How to measure:** Fractions of fields documented, existence of current data dictionary, and schema version coverage. **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

47. How relevant is the Metadata & Documentation Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

48. To what extent does the Metadata & Documentation Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

49. How clear and well-defined is the Metadata & Documentation Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

50. How applicable and easy to use is the Metadata & Documentation Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

51. To what extent is the Metadata & Documentation Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Interoperability Data Quality Domain** in MBD

Interoperability—Ability to exchange and reuse data across systems. **Definition:** Ensuring conformance with the Health Level Seven International (HL7), Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR), and Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) through APIs, which are supported by precise semantic and syntactic mapping, allows healthcare data to be shared across diverse platforms while safeguarding consistency and interpretability and the **attributes, such as syntactic interoperability, semantic interoperability, vocabulary standardization, terminology mapping, identifier consistency, structural mapping, use of interchange standards, data format uniformity.** **Example:** A hospital successfully sent FHIR-formatted immunization records to a national registry and received acknowledgment . **How to measure:** % successful standard exchanges, FHIR conformance score, and mapping error rate. **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

52. How relevant is the Interoperability Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

53. To what extent does the Interoperability Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

54. How clear and well-defined is the Interoperability Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

55. How applicable and easy to use is the Interoperability Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

56. To what extent is the Interoperability Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **User-Centric/Interpretive Data Quality Domain** in MBD

User-Centric/Interpretive—How do end-users perceive and understand data? **Definition:** Readability, explainability, visualization clarity, and cognitive load considerations so that clinicians, patients and analysts can correctly interpret the data and model outputs and the **attributes, such as interpretability, readability, usability, learnability, labeling clarity, visual interpretability, context awareness, navigation simplicity** . **Example:** A dashboard showing an AI risk score together with the top contributing variables (explainability) and an easy-to-read legend . **How to measure:** clinician task success, readability scores, and % outputs with explanations. **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

57. How relevant is the User-Centric/Interpretive Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

58. To what extent does the User-Centric/Interpretive Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

59. How clear and well-defined is the User-Centric/Interpretive Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

60. How applicable and easy to use is the User-Centric/Interpretive Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

61. To what extent is the User-Centric/Interpretive Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

Evaluation and Validation of the **Systematic Infrastructure Data Quality Domain** in MBD

Systematic Infrastructure—What the platform guarantees. **Definition:** Hardware, cloud/cluster architecture, Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) pipelines, logging/monitoring, and operational controls that keep data flow stable, available, and intact and the **attributes, such as system scalability, data pipeline integrity, high-availability (HA), fault tolerance, monitoring & auditability, infrastructure interoperability, data load balancing, cloud compatibility.** **Example:** A high-availability EHR cluster with automated failover, load-balancing for imaging uploads, and pipeline checkpoints that prevent data loss during peak admissions. **Measuring:** uptime %, ETL success rate, and pipeline error counts . **Eight representative attributes per domain, selected based on their frequency in the literature, were used to illustrate key aspects for expert validation**

62. How relevant is the Systematic Infrastructure Data Quality Domain in the context of Medical Big Data? *

	Not Relevant	Slightly Relevant	Moderately Relevant	Highly Relevant	Extremely Relevant
Relevance	<input type="radio"/>				

63. To what extent does the Systematic Infrastructure Data Quality Domain adequately cover all necessary data quality attributes in Medical Big Data? *

	Not Complete	Slightly Complete	Moderately Complete	Highly Complete	Fully Complete
Completeness	<input type="radio"/>				

64. How clear and well-defined is the Systematic Infrastructure Data Quality Domain and its associated attributes? *

	Not Clear	Slightly Clear	Moderately Clear	Very Clear	Extremely Clear
Clarity	<input type="radio"/>				

65. How applicable and easy to use is the Systematic Infrastructure Data Quality Domain in real-world medical big data systems? *

	Not applicable and difficult to use	Slightly applicable and difficult to use	Moderately applicable and usable	Highly applicable and easy to use	Extremely applicable and very easy to use
Applicability and Usability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

66. To what extent is the Systematic Infrastructure Data Quality Domain sufficient as an independent domain within Medical Big Data? *

	Not Sufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Moderately Sufficient	Highly Sufficient	Fully Sufficient
Sufficiency	<input type="radio"/>				

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Microsoft. The data you submit will be sent to the form owner.

 Microsoft Forms